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Research Article

**IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON HEALTH-RELATED QUALITY OF
LIFE IN PATIENTS WITH CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE.**¹Dr Ayesha Shafeeque, ²Dr Muneeb Anwar, ³Dr Ahad Ali Khan.¹MBBS, Ameer Ud Din Medical College, Lahore., ^{2,3}MBBS, Nawaz Sharif Medical College, Gujrat.**Article Received:** October 2020**Accepted:** November 2020**Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Coronavirus causes severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2, it is a global pandemic and it enter cells by angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 receptors. Patients having cardiovascular diseases have high risks for myocardial injury from infection.

Causes: High levels of bio marks including cytokine storm, troponin T levels due to attack of SARS-CoV-2, causing myocardial issues to the patients.

Treatment: Drugs such as remdesivir, chloroquine, hydroxochloroquine and many other drugs are used to treat patients and to save them from such threats of covid-19.

Results: In most cases, male having an average age of 59.8 having corona virus have threats to acquire coronary artery disease, heart failure. So, older people have more chances to have myocardial injury.

Conclusion: COVID-19 has worse effect on mental health of patients with cardiovascular diseases, and it is a pandemic.

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INTRODUCTION:

Recently, the researches showed that older people with cardiovascular disorders are at a higher risk of death due to covid-19. Coronavirus can also cause heart diseases to patients having no heart issues. Covid-19 patients may get cardiovascular diseases by many mechanism. The most reported cardiovascular abnormality in patients of covid-19 is acute cardiac injury approximately (8-12% of all patients). This abnormality has elevated the risk of death of the patients.[3]

The recent research has showed that approximately 20% patients of covid-19 has cardiac injury. In most cases, increased troponin T levels in covid-19 patients is observed than the normal persons. Furthermore, the older people have showed high levels of troponin T, with heart issues like hypertension, chronic kidney diseases etc.[3]

Approximately 23% patients have showed incidence of acute heart failure. The symptoms including acute and fulminant myocarditis and many more are observed. Some functional receptor of coronavirus such as ACE2 identify its indirect link with cardiovascular pathology. Myocytes gives the binding site for SARS-CoV-2 to receptors ACE2. So, myocyte damage is a prominent mechanism of viral attack.[3]

ACE2 is a protein, it has an important role in immune system in a normal person and it can also cause hypertension. It helps SARS-CoV-2 to bind with myocyte and alters its functions, it can also cause increase in its secretion.[3]

Researches demonstrated that there are two forms of myocardial injury due to coronavirus. One study indicate that hs-cTnl level is 8.8pg/mL. Median hs-cTnl in survivors did not change, but it is elevated to 24.7pg/mL on seventh day to 55.7pg/mL on thirteenth day to 134.5pg/mL on nineteenth day and to 290.9pg/mL on twenty second day among non survivors. The time of death in median form is between 15 to 20 days.[1]

The increased hs-cTnl level with other bio marks, shows the chances of secondary hemophagocytic lymphonistiosytosis more than myocardial injury. [1]

Symptoms:

It has been demonstrated that 35% patients of covid-19 have hypertension and 17% have coronary heart diseases according to National Health Commission of China. [1]

The reports of patients dominantly shows the heart symptoms that demonstrate a different form of stress cardiomyopathy .[1]

Case-I:

A man having chest pain with ST-segment elevation on his ECG, without coronary obstruction. His echocardiogram noticed left ventricular dysfunction and elevated cardiac biomarkers (troponin T > 10ng/mL, NT-proBNP > 21000pg/mL).[1]

Cure:

Giving him therapeutic cure, which have intra-venous immunoglobulin and steroids, ejection fraction and cardiac biomarkers normalized the patient up to a time of three weeks. [1]

Case-II:

A sixty-three years old man of china having no cardiac history, was observed to have severe respiratory manifestation and symptoms of fulminant myocarditis with an increased left ventricle (diameter of 6.1 cm) and its function was depressed. He had elevated troponin and NT-proBNP.[1]

Cure:

He was exposed to extracorporeal membrane oxygenation and was given with intravenous immunoglobulin, antiviral therapy, steroids and renal replacement therapy. He was recovered within two weeks. [1]

Common points of case-I and case-II:

- Above the two cases, both men were cured with glucocorticoids but its impact is still unclear. [1]
- The WHO did not recommend glucocorticoids to cure the disease.[1]

Case-III:

A man with his history of type two diabetes mellitus, having cough, pleuritic chest pain, progressive shortness of breath for one week staying outside hospital. His white blood cell counts for 9000 per μ L with 11% band forms, 11% lymphocytes, a venous lactate of 1.7 mmol/L with normal renal and liver function. His test for covid-19 was positive his left ventricle was functioning normal. He was successfully cardioverted. [4]

On an average, the patient was observed to have cardiac illness, he was given mechanical ventilation. But still his case is studying by doctors.[4]

Case-IV:

A man that had transplanted his kidney in 2010, and having history heart transplantation in 2007, it was

observed that he had fever, dry cough, shortness of breath for nine days. His immunosuppression shows tacrolimus 5mg twice, mycophenolate, mofetil 250mg twice, prednisone 5mg daily.[4]

Observation showed white blood cells 2750 per μL with lymphopenia and serum creatinine 4.3mg/dL, ferritin 1514ng/mL. He had coronavirus positive test. [4]

Cure:

He was treated with hydroxychloroquine and azithromycin 500mg daily. After staying for 7 days in hospital, he was discharged.[4]

Causes:

- Heart diseases may result from cytokine storm manifestation due to elevated levels of interleukin-6 (IL-6), ferritin, lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), and D-dimer or myocardial dysfunction from direct attack of SARS-CoV-2 on the hearts of the patients.[1]
- Patients of cardiovascular disease having covid-19 have high mortality rates. [5]
- It can cause pericyte injury related to heart failure.[5]
- Covid-19 patients have shown the confirmed presence of diseases such as diabetes, cerebrovascular disease, ischemic heart disease and hypertension having severe form of disease (approximately 38.7% vs. 21.0%). [6]
- Italy was the most affected country, the virus started from china then vigorously started spreading to Europe and Asia, unfortunately, and became pandemic.[6] Its confirmed patients are >1200000. [3]
- Covid-19 virus promotes acute coronary syndrome, arrhythmias, cardiogenic shock, myocarditis, heart failure, systematic thromboembolism mainly.[6]

Impacts:

- Risk factors was prominent in patients with SARS-CoV-2. In covid-19 patients cardiovascular disorders have percentage of 8-11 of all the cases. There is a 12-fold higher risk of mortality. From china it have been reported that covid-19 patients having cardiovascular disease are at higher risk specifically in severe manifestation. [7]
- The hospitalized covid-19 patients of china have widespread of cardiovascular disease (12.11%), hypertension (16.37%), smoking (7.63%), diabetes (7.87%) respectively.[7]

- Recently, Chinese covid-19 patients that are incident of cardiovascular disorders have critical situations as compared to those having only covid-19.[7]
- Although many reports have identified that cardiovascular disorders are among the worst applicable prognostic facts for covid-19.[7]
- The fatality rate in Italy which, was first western country to be affected by covid-19, was very high.[7]
- The died covid-19 patients have comorbidities including ischaemic heart disease (28%), atrial fibrillation (23%).[7]
- Covid-19 can cause cardiac injury in variable proportion among patients, the presence of cardiovascular disorder can impart the presence of this condition.[7]

Treatment:

In Japan, the serine protease inhibitor comostat mesylate, approved for chronic pancreatitis and postoperative reflux esophagitis, but it has been observed to block transmembrane protease serine 2 activity and it do not allow SARS-CoV-2 entry into cells. It prevents SARS-CoV-2 entry thus preventing the disease activation. [1]

A broad spectrum antiviral agent, Remdesivir, interrupts RNA replication as a nucleotide analog. It has been observed that it has reduced disease severity in primates against SARS-CoV-2. Other drugs such as chloroquine and hydroxychloroquine is been used for treatment against SARS-CoV-2 cell entry, blocking in vitro for rheumatoid arthritis. [1]

Drugs such as oseltamivir 75 mg two times a day, ribavirin 0.5 gram two times a day, umifenovir 0.2 g three times a day, moxifloxacin 0.4 gram daily and methylprednisolone 40-80 mg daily and respiratory supports are main treatment methods for covid-19 patients.[8]

Preventions:

People should be aware of local SARS-CoV-2 cases and relative symptoms. They should have excellent hand hygiene in addition to avoidance of sick contact and crowding are prime measures to prevent the spreading of viral disease.[9]

The WHO has advised that everyone should have frequently and completely washed their hands, they should not touch their face and to practice respiratory hygiene.[9]

Despite it is compulsory for everyone to obey the above instruction but the patients of cardiovascular

disease should have to obey these instructions strictly to low the severity of disease.[9]

By gaining hygienic skills, keeping social distance can reduce the spread of infection. Using gloves and face masks are important to prevent covid-19 strongly, especially in patients having cardiovascular disease and for nurses and doctors that are taking care of them.[7]

Furthermore, healthy diet, improved life style, regular exercise, uniform check and balance of your health should be necessary for patients having cardiovascular disease.[7]

Complications:

There are thromboembolic events as high as 31% reported in Italy at ICU-level care. Acute arterial thrombotic events such as cerebrovascular accident, have been identified in covid-19 patients.[10]

The most common thrombotic event identifies the pulmonary embolism. The patients having these complications have higher threat of death.[10]

Pulmonary embolism imparts to higher rate of cardiac injury in severe covid-19 infection as right ventricle may lead to high levels of cardiac biomarkers during thromboembolic events.[10]

Moreover, people having critical illness would have prolonged thrombophylaxis.[10]

Patients of covid-19 have mainly increased TnT levels having cardiovascular disorder as compared to patients having only covid-19.[8]

Patients of cardiovascular disorders having covid-19 have higher threat of death than those having only covid-19.[8]

Limitations:

There are many limitations.

- Our information regarding covid-19 and cardiovascular patient requires verification.[8]
- The research of the patients is incomplete because of limited conditions in isolation wards of covid-19.[8]
- The clinical approaches for assessment is limited to covid-19. To identify the cause of death of the patients due to Myocardial injury is difficult.[8]

- To generate effective treatment of myocardial injury of covid-19 patients we have to require long term observation and meaningful information.[8]

CONCLUSIONS:

Cardiovascular disease and covid-19 shows a prominent connection. Although, covid-19 is prominently a respiratory disease, but patients may get heart issues during the course of viral attack. So, cardiovascular disease is of prime importance to cure a patient of covid-19. Patients of covid-19 have to suffer more critical conditions. One-fourth of total patients of covid-19 have heart issues, they roughly impart for 4% death rate due to viral attack.[3]

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